

FULL PAPER

Title: Independent Judiciary System

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Introduction In modern world wherein India sees itself as the fastest growing economy for its size, along with being the 6th richest economy in the world in process of being the 5th richest and wherein India also aspires to be the permanent member of United Nations Security Council, It is highly pertinent to ensure that internal law and order is maintained and justice is not only served but it also is shown to be served as well. After all it is the faith in the system that shall sustain the system.

However there have been instances wherein the independence and impartiality of judiciary has been in doubt, the instances have been when the judges of supreme court came out in press alleging the bias of chief justice, moreover even one of the mediators chosen in Ayodhya Ram janmabhoomi case lacks the adequate credentials of his peers along with the time of the deadline of mediation coinciding just before the end of elections does seem bit conspicuous. In addition to it the collegiums system's decisions not being stable recently coupled with the supreme court judges getting administrative posts after their retirement creates doubts in peoples mind as to whether the Indian judicial system is truly independent or not.

Justice should not only be administered but it also must seem to be administered in order to ensure that there is no iota of doubt regarding the independence of judiciary among common people and the critics alike. Judiciary being the guardian of constitution and the final interpreter of basic structure has the great responsibility to be impartial and independent. In this paper the author does point out some measures which can be taken by the judiciary to ensure its independence which are highly feasible as well.

Keywords: judiciary, impartiality, independence, doubt, problems, probable measures

Of course the author of the paper does recognise the fact that the problem in question is a very complex one and there is no silver bullet to solve all the issues at hand. The paper does try to make an attempt to initiate the efforts to solve the problems at hand.

In the following paper, the author is going to discuss to begin with the role of the able judiciary and how the judiciray has maintained its independence so far.

In second part the author is going to discuss as to why the independence of judiciary is very important, followed by the recent developments which does raise the question as to whether the judiciary is certainly independent or not....and answering the same finally i am going to conclude in the third part the measures which can be taken to further strengthen the independence of judiciary.

Current Scenario: Chief Justice of India Dipak Misra had remarked during farewell function that Indian judiciary is the "most robust institution" in the world and young lawyers were

assets having potential to develop the jurisprudence. "Our judiciary has been strongest judiciary in the world having capability to handle mind boggling number of cases,"

Independence of Judiciary: Judicial independence is the concept that the judiciary should be independent from the other branches of government. That is, courts should not be subject to improper influence from the other branches of government or from private or partisan interests

The Constitution of India makes judiciary truly independent.

The constitution of India adopts diverse devices to ensure the independence of the judiciary in keeping with both the doctrines of constitutional and Parliamentary sovereignty. Elaborated provision are in place for ensuring the independent position of the Judges of the Supreme Court and the High Courts.

Firstly, the judges of the Supreme Court and the High Courts have **to take an oath** before entering office that they will faithfully perform their duties without fear, favour, affection, ill-will, and defend the constitution of India and the laws.

Recognition of the doctrine of constitutional sovereignty is implicit in this oath.

Secondly, the process of **appointment of judges also ensures the independence of judiciary in India**. The judges of the Supreme Court and the High Courts are appointed by the President. The constitution of India has made it obligatory on the President to make the appointments in consultation with the highest judicial authorities. He of course takes advice of the Cabinet. The constitution also prescribes necessary qualifications for such appointments. The constitution tries to make the appointments unbiased by political considerations.

Thirdly, the Constitution provides for the **security of tenure of Judges**. The judges of the Supreme Court and the High Court's serve "**during good behavior**" and not during the pleasure of the President, as is the case with other high Government officials. They cannot be arbitrarily removed by the President. They may be removed from office only through impeachment. A Judge can be removed on the ground of proved misbehavior or incapacity on a report by both Houses of Parliament supported by a special majority.

Fourthly, their **salaries and allowances are charged upon the Consolidated Fund of India**. Further, the salaries and allowances of Judges of Supreme court and High courts cannot be reduced during their tenure, except during a financial emergency under Article 360 of the constitution.

Fifthly, the **activities of the Judges** cannot be discussed by the executive or the legislature, except in case of removal of them.

Sixth, the **retirement age is 65 years for Supreme court judges and 62 years** for High court judges. Such long tenure enable the judges to function impartially and independently.

Seventh, a retired **Supreme court judge cannot practice engage in legal practice** in any court in India. However, a retired High court judge can practice law in a state other than the state in which he served as a High Court judge. These restrictions ensure that a retired judge is not able to influence the decision of the courts.

The **hierarchy of Judicial system** in India plays an important role in maintaining the independence of judiciary. Supreme Court is the highest court for justice. Then, there are

High Court and District Courts in every states. Then, there are People's courts known as Lok Adalats. If no decision is reached at these Lok Adalats, then the cases move to courts.

Thus constitution provides adequate safeguards to ensure independence of judicial system. It is not only that the Indian constitution strengthens the Indian Judicial System but Indian Constitution also empowers Indian Constitution with various important tools to not only be the defender and protector of "Basic Structure of Constitution" so as to ensure:

यतो धर्मस्ततो जयः॥

Where there is truth (dharma), there is victory (justice)

Judiciary as the Interpreter of the Constitution:

The Constitution of India is a written and enacted constitution. The right to interpret and clarify the Constitution has been given to the Supreme Court. It is the final interpreter of the provisions of the Constitution of India.

Judicial Review:

The Constitution of India is the supreme law of the land. The power of judicial review of supreme court is vested in Articles 32 and article 136 of the constitution. Moreover articles 226 and 227 of the constitution empowers high courts with the power of judicial review.

The Supreme Court acts as the interpreter and protector of the Constitution. It is the guardian of the fundamental rights and freedoms of the people. For performing this role, it exercises the power of judicial review. The Supreme Court has the power to determine the constitutional validity of all laws. It can reject any such law which is held to be unconstitutional. High Courts also exercise this power.

Guardian of Fundamental Rights:

Part III of the constitution of India from Articles 12 to 35 are enshrined with the fundamental rights. Indian judiciary acts as the guardian of fundamental rights and freedoms of the people. The people have the Right to Constitutional Remedies under which they can seek the protection of the courts for preventing a violation or for meeting any threat to their rights. The Supreme Court and the High Courts have the power to issue writs for this purpose.

Judicial Activism:

Indian Judicial System has been becoming more and more active. The Supreme Court has been coming out with judicial decisions and directives aimed at active protection of public interest and human rights. Judiciary has been giving directives to public officials for ensuring a better security for the rights of the public. The Public Interest Litigation system has been picking up. The system of Lok Adalats has also taken a proper shape and health. The introduction of Public Interest Litigation by Justice VR Krishna Iyer further increased the scope of Judicial activism

Public Interest Litigation System:

Under this system the courts of law in India can initiate and enforce action for securing any significant public or general interest which is being adversely affected or is likely to be so by the action of any agency, public or private. Under it any citizen or a group or a voluntary

organisation, or even a court herself, can bring to notice any case demanding action for protecting and satisfying a public interest.

Current Scenario: Time and again it has been stated that with great power comes great responsibility. Independence of judiciary is of vital importance indeed as supreme court is not just the custodian of the constitution, but also the guardian of our fundamental rights along with the final interpreter of the very “basic structure” of the constitution.

However time and again Indian Judiciary has shown lack of accountability in issues more than one:

Many questions arise as to what has gone wrong with the system. Pt. Nehru has said in a statement, “*Judges of the Supreme Court sit on ivory towers far removed from ordinary men and know nothing about them.*” Judges are also humans after all and can make errors all the time. So how can one achieve accountability in such a system?

Thus, the problems and solutions with judicial accountability have been discussed below.

1. IMPEACHMENT

Article 124(4) of the Indian Constitution specifies the process of impeachment that is removal of a judge of Supreme Court on the grounds of proven misbehaviour or incapacity. This is the only possible and available mechanism in the judicial system of making the higher judiciary accountable for their actions. According to the Judges Enquiry Act, 1968, a complaint against a judge can be made by passing a resolution signed by either 100 members of Lok Sabha or 50 members of Rajya Sabha. Then there is a three member committee two judges from the Supreme Court and the other chief justice of India. Investigations have to be made before passing a resolution. In the procedure for removal or impeachment of the judges, a resolution must be passed in each house of parliament by the total majority of members of the house and not less than two-thirds majority of the house present and voting. The process must take place in a single sitting. The resolution has to be presented before the president for his approval.

No judge has been impeached till date. However this does mean that there is no corruption in the system. The whole impeachment process is considered to be a failure as it is so lengthy and clumsy.

Justice Ramaswamy's case:

This was the first impeachment case ever against a Supreme Court judge. Justice V. Ramaswamy was appointed as the chief justice of Punjab and Haryana High Court on November 12, 1987. He got promoted to Supreme Court in October, 1989. In 1990, there were complaints about him in press that he had spent a large amount of office money on himself and misused it grossly. In February 1991, 108 members of the Bharatiya Janta Party (opposition party), signed and submitted a notice of motion to the speaker of Lok Sabha for the removal of Justice Ramaswamy. However, Ramaswamy survived the impeachment because of the huge support from the Southern region MPs. 196 MPs voted for the motion which was less than what was required, that is, two-thirds. The motion failed regardless of the two yearlong proceedings that took place and unanimous votes from the opposition.

Another issue is that the investigating committees also consist of judges and they are hesitant to charge their colleagues for corruption. They all work together like a union. The answer to this problem can be forming a National Judicial Commission, an independent body having its own investigating mechanism.

2. CORRUPTION IN JUDICIARY

Judicial corruption includes dishonest use or 'misuse' of judicial powers by the court authorities leading to unfair and unjust judgements. Due to corruption in judiciary, the public is deprived of the right to fair trial and right to equality.

Justice K. Veeraswamy's case:

Justice K. Veeraswamy was the chief justice of Madras High Court. A case was filed against him by the CBI under Prevention of Corruption Act, charging him for possession of assets inconsistent with his income sources. The Madras High Court referred the case to the Supreme Court for dealing with important issues of law. The Supreme Court laid down some stern guidelines for the protection of judicial independence.

1. No F.I.R. can be registered against a Judge or Chief Justice of the High Court, or a Judge of the Supreme Court without the sanction of the Chief Justice of India in the matter.
2. It was held that the Supreme Court is not a court of limited jurisdiction of only dispute settling, and that the court has been a law maker and it is the courts responsibility and duty to apply the existing law in a form more favourable to the independence of the judiciary.
3. It was also said that any complaint against a Judge and its investigation by the CBI, if given publicity will have a far reaching impact on the judge and the litigant public therefore there is need of a judicious use of taking action under the Prevention of Corruption Act.

The Supreme Court's judgement in this case has been criticized on the ground that this is sheer misuse of judicial independence and it completely overlooks the concept of judicial accountability. It provides an unfair shield to the judges for arbitrary behaviour and use of judicial powers.

Justice Soumitra Sen's case:

Soumitra Sen is a former judge of Calcutta High Court. There were allegations against him that he had misappropriated Rs. 32 lakhs as a court worker in a case from 1993 between *Steel Authority of India Limited (SAIL) and Shipping Corporation of India*. A three judge committee was formed which found him guilty of depositing public funds into his personal account. In 2006, he returned the money due to passing of the High Court order. A year later the Chief Justice of India, KG Balkrishnan recommended his impeachment to the Prime Minister. This was the 2nd case after the Ramaswamy case where the parliament initiated impeachment proceedings against a High Court judge. In 2009, 53 Members of Parliament passed a resolution in the Rajya Sabha for the removal of Justice Sen. In 2011 the Rajya Sabha passed the motion with a majority of 189 votes in favor of the motion. Before the motion could be passed in Lok Sabha, Justice Soumitra Sen resigned. He was found guilty of misappropriating public funds and misrepresenting the facts to the court.

Sexual Harassment Cases:

A retired Supreme Court judge and former Chief Justice of the Orissa High Court, Judge AK Ganguly was accused by a woman intern for sexually harassing her. He was found guilty by the three judge committee even though he continually denied all allegations. He resigned from the West Bengal Human Rights Commission in 2014.

In another recent case, a sexual harassment complaint was filed against Madhya Pradesh High Court judge SK Gangeela. The committee has investigated the matter and 58 Rajya Sabha MPs have passed a resolution for his impeachment.

Such cases of gross misconduct on behalf of higher judiciary judges are a shame for the Indian Judiciary. High court and Supreme Court judges that are supposed to provide justice to the society are themselves involved in such criminal activities is highly unfortunate. They must not be given the immunity from proper criminal proceedings. They must be tried like any other offender. If such cases keep on rising then there would be no accountability left in the judiciary.

3. CONTEMPT OF COURT

The Meghalaya high court Friday sentenced *Shillong Times* editor Patricia Mukhim and publisher Shoba Chaudhuri to sit in the corner of the court room till the rising of the court besides imposing a fine of Rs 2 lakh each in a contempt case. The case relates to an article published by the paper on the perks and facilities for retired judges and their families. A division bench headed by Chief Justice Mohammad Yaqoob Mir warned that if the two persons failed to deposit the amount they will have to undergo six months simple imprisonment and the paper will be banned. "In exercise of the power vested on us by Article 215 of the constitution of India, we sentence both the contemnors to sit in the corner of the court room till the rising of the court and impose a fine of Rs 2 lakh each which is to be deposited with the Registry within a week and then to be deposited in the welfare fund of this high court," the bench said.

However the supreme court fortunately intervened reassuring that it is the guardian of freedom of speech and expression.

But there have been instances where even supreme court has taken a drastic measure as in the case of

Arundhati Roy issue:

Arundhati Roy and Medha Pathkar were activists from Narmada Bachao Andolan who protested against the Supreme Court's order of increasing the height of Sardar Sarovar dam by 90 meters which would further lead to destruction of nearby villages. Ms Arundhati Roy and other protesters participated in a dharna and gave a demonstration outside the court criticizing the court's order. The Supreme Court without giving any prior notification or chance to be heard served Ms Roy with a notice of contempt of court and violation of principles of natural justice. Their advocate Mr. Prashant Bhushan stated that the court had abused its powers of contempt. Ms Roy was merely practicing her rights of freedom of speech and expression. The court's order clearly violates her rights. The court without any

justification cannot practice its powers of contempt arbitrarily. How does that justify judicial accountability?

4. **RIGHT TO INFORMATION(RTI) AND JUDICIARY**

In the famous judgement of *Indira Gandhi v Raj Narain*, the Supreme Court stated the importance of Right to Information and explained eloquently how the right was guaranteed to individuals by the constitution. The Supreme Court held that right to receive and impart information is a part of the right to freedom of speech under the constitution. The court rejected the government's claim for privacy over the Blue Book that contained information about security measures for Prime Minister in Indira Gandhi's case. The Supreme Court stated that the government had a responsibility to not keep any secrets regarding public functions and disclose all information that is related to public functionaries.

However the Indian judiciary has shown some serious hypocrisy and double standards about practicing Right to Information.

In the list of cases to be heard by the Constitution bench of the Supreme Court from March 27th, the Supreme Court has included its own appeal against a Delhi High Court judgment that had held that the Supreme Court and the Chief Justice of India are "public authorities" under the Right to Information Act. Three Judge bench of Delhi High Court comprising the then Chief Justice A P Shah, Justice Vikramjeet Sen and Justice S Muralidhar had upheld the single bench judgment that Supreme Court and the Chief Justice of India have statutory duty to furnish information sought by citizens regarding the functioning and administration of the Supreme Court. The single bench had dismissed the challenge against the order of Central Information Commission whereby it had directed the Supreme Court CPIO to provide the information requested by Subhash Chandra Agarwal for supply of information concerning declaration of personal assets by the Judges of the Supreme Court.

These appeals, though filed in the year 2010, were referred to the Constitution bench only in August 2016 by a three judge bench headed by Justice Ranjan Gogoi. The bench also referred the following questions formulated by a bench of Justice B. Sudershan Reddy and Justice SS Nijjar along with the appeals.

Whether the concept of independence of judiciary requires and demands the prohibition of furnishing of the information sought? Whether the information sought for amounts to interference in the functioning of the judiciary? Whether the information sought for cannot be furnished to avoid any erosion in the credibility of the decisions and to ensure a free and frank expression of honest opinion by all the constitutional functionaries, which is essential for effective consultation and for taking the right decision? Whether the information sought for is exempt under Section 8(i)(j) of the Right to Information Act?

5. **JUDICIAL ACTIVISM VS JUDICIAL OVERREACH**

Although, Judiciary has done a commendable job in delivering justice through judicial activism, however there were some recent Supreme Court verdicts and orders, which seem too tough to be implemented and may remain just on papers such as the following:

- i) Supreme Court verdict on the entry of women of all ages into the Sabarmila temple.
- ii) The order fixing timings for bursting of fire crackers during diwali.
- iii) Speedy disposal of pending cases against legislators and law makers(former and sitting).

- iv) Witness protection scheme of 2018

6.APPOINTMENT OF JUDGES.

Indian Judiciary has by and large maintained its independence through the first judges case, and subsequently asserted the same through second and third judges case. Moreover the honourable judiciary went so far as to declare NJAC unconstitutional to ensure that judiciary remains impartial and independent.

Moreover the collegiums system lacks the stability, transparency and accountability to ensure that judiciary works in a fair and impartial manner.

Recently, the collegiums system was there in controversy again as former chief justices of India, a sitting supreme court judge and var council of india has taken exception collegiums unuasual action of revisiting decisions made on december12 th last year.

The official reasons are in the public domain in the form of a resolution on January 10. It claims that even though some decisions were made on December 12, “the required consultations could not be undertaken and completed” in view of the winter vacation. When the collegium met again on January 5/6, its composition had changed following the retirement of Justice Madan B. Lokur. It was then decided that it would be “appropriate” to have a fresh look at the matter, as well as the “additional material”. The only rationale for the names of Rajasthan High Court Chief Justice Pradeep Nandrajog and Delhi High Court Chief Justice Rajendra Menon being left out is the claim that new material had surfaced. However, it is not clear what the material is and how it affected their suitability.

Former Chief Justice of India R.M. Lodha is right in underscoring the institutional nature of decisions by the collegium. Can the retirement of one judge be a ground to withdraw a considered decision, even if some consultations were incomplete? There is little surprise in the disquiet in legal circles.

Thus there is an urgent need to relook at the collegiums system.

1. FORMATION OF MORE ACCOUNTABLE APPOINTING MECHANISM

The 80th and 121st Law Commission Reports of India have made the suggestion to form NJC. It is supposed to consist of 5 members:

1. One member nominated by all the Supreme Court judges
2. One member nominated by the Chief Justices of the High Courts
3. One member nominated by the cabinet of ministers
4. One member nominated by the speaker and the Leader of Opposition of both the houses
5. The last one member nominated by Chief Vigilance Commissioner of the Central Vigilance Commission (CVC), Comptroller and Auditor General (CAG) and the Chairperson of the National Human Rights Commission (NHRC)

The NJC shall have its own investigative mechanism that shall investigate in the matters of removal of judges. Also the NJC will select the judges for appointment in HC and SC, the information of which will be available to the public. In this way the independence of judiciary is maintained and its accountability to the public too.

2. JUDICIAL ACCOUNTABILITY BILL

The bill was introduced in Lok Sabha on December 1, 2010.

The bill shall lay down judicial standards and provide for accountability of the judiciary. It will establish certain mechanisms to investigate the complaints made against the judges individually. Also, it shall provide a mechanism for the removal of judges. It will replace the old Judges Inquiry Act, 1968.

A five member commission shall be appointed by the president on the recommendation of the prime minister and its cabinet of ministers including the leader of opposition and a minority member.

Declaration of assets of judges' shall be made mandatory.

When a complaint is received against the judges, it shall go to the investigating committee. If the charges are serious then the committee can ask the judge to resign, and if he refuses the case will move forward towards the process of removal. All the investigation proceeding information shall be made available to the public.

3. **JUDICIAL RESTRAINT** It is important for the judiciary to practice judicial restraint for maintaining the balance between the different organs of democracy. The courts must be concerned with legality and law.

4. **AMENDING THE CONTEMPT OF COURT ACT** The Contempt of Court Act has a lot of loopholes and it gives arbitrary powers to the judiciary. Few suggestions for the amendment were made. The accused must be provided with a reasonable opportunity to defend himself.

5. **JUDGES MUST NOT BE ALLOWED TO TAKE UP ADMINISTRATIVE POSTS AFTER RETIREMENT.**

This shall preserve the integrity and impartiality of the honourable judges.

6. **JUDGES MUST BE BROUGHT UNDER THE PURVIEW OF RTI** as stated by the honourable Delhi high Court

Conclusion: Justice should not only be administered but it also must seem to be administered in order to ensure that there is no iota of doubt regarding the independence of judiciary among common people and the critics alike. Judiciary being the guardian of constitution and the final interpreter of basic structure has the great responsibility to be impartial and independent

End Note: The entire paper is based on secondary references from which an attempt has been made to understand the nature of Judicial independence and the need for bringing in judicial accountability.

